

POLITICAL SCIENCES

FEATURES OF INFORMATION SECURITY OF UKRAINE, THE USA AND THE PRC

Koshelnyk V.

PhD student

V.N. Karazin Kharkiv National University

Kharkiv, Ukraine

ORCID: 0009-0001-9479-1776

Abstract

The work examines the issue of information security at the national and regional levels. It was analyzed that a favorable information environment, protection against cyber attacks is an important element of national security. The main problems of Ukraine in the field of information security are considered using the example of information attacks from the Russian Federation. Two models of information security were studied: democratic and totalitarian; the peculiarities of their use in the United States of America, the People's Republic of China and Ukraine are determined. The administrative and legal mechanism for ensuring information security in Ukraine is analyzed compared to foreign experience. At the same time, information security, in the context of the development of the information society, means the state of security of information resources, databases, information technologies and technical means intended for the collection, processing, storage and transmission of information necessary for the realization of the rights and legitimate interests of subjects of information activity, individuals, societies and states in the information space from the influence of a special type of threats that appear in the form of purposeful or spontaneous activity in the information environment. The emphasis is on the fact that information security acts as a system of social relations that realizes the connection between the interests of the individual, society and the state in the field of information and the legal provision of their protection, which includes the state of security of civil society mainly in the information space and information and telecommunications infrastructure from possible internal and external threats.

Keywords: information, information security, information space, information resources, information technologies.

Introduction.

To date, when the development of technology has reached a high level, the threats to the regional and national security of countries have grown proportionally to it. Therefore, information security acts as one of the main links of society's security. In connection with this, the world public and scientific community felt the need to join forces and create reliable protection against information attacks and form a safe information space.

The topic of information security is quite large, so it is necessary to single out certain links of it that require increased attention of scientists. Currently, the problems of media protection, which have become the subject of discussions, are being studied by many Ukrainian scientists, among them: O. Astakhov, V. Bogdanovych, M. Dmytrenko, V. Husarov, O. Panchenko, M. Yermoshin, V. Horbulin, A. Semenchenko, S. Mosov, I. Romanchenko and others. Among the foreign scientists involved in this problem were: N. Bostrom, I. Bachilo, A. Benoit, Z. Bauman, D. Bel, G. le Bon, K. Vrochynski, T. Eriksen, P. Drucker, R. Zemba, M. Castells, N. Luchi, G. Kuby, K. Lidl, K. Liederman, L. Karvaliks, R. Kuznyar, and others. At the moment, the issues of information security have not been studied to the end, and therefore, require increased attention from scientists.

The rapid growth of scale and variety of information brings to mankind both many new opportunities for self-realization of an individual and society, as well as a lot of new risks and threats. As for the level of information security in Ukraine, it is in a critical situation.

Information war, information expansion, cyber terrorism turned out to be a serious test for Ukraine, for which it was not ready.

Main text.

The information society, towards which humanity is rapidly moving, qualitatively changes the meaning of the concept of information, expanding its potential as a positive resource, and revealing its sharply negative qualities. The study of information as a strategic resource for human development has shown that it can be reliable and relevant, new and outdated, but it cannot be transmitted, received or preserved in its pure form. Any information does not exist by itself, it has its own medium, the ways of its transmission are within the framework of communication channels. In a very broad sense, «information» means the storage of any information and data on physical media or reproduction in electronic format [1].

Currently, the current legislation of Ukraine does not contain a definition of the term «information security», however, as stated in the «Information Security Strategy of Ukraine», it is a component of the national security of Ukraine, contributes to the protection of state sovereignty, territorial integrity, the democratic constitutional order, and other vital human interests, society and the state [2].

The Law of Ukraine «On National Security» states that state policy in the spheres of national security and defense is aimed at ensuring Ukraine's military, foreign policy, state, economic, informational, environmental security, cyber security, etc. [3].

Instead, O. Panchenko gives his definition of the

concept of «information security» – it is a state of protection of the vital interests of the individual, society and the state, in which the harm due to incompleteness, untimeliness and unreliability of information, negative informational impact and consequences of the functioning of information technologies is minimized, and also due to unauthorized dissemination of information. The importance of protecting information security is emphasized in the Constitution of Ukraine: «Protecting the sovereignty and territorial integrity of Ukraine, ensuring its economic and information security are the most important functions of the state, the business of the entire Ukrainian people» [4, p. 672].

We share the opinion of the majority of scientists who believe that information security is a part of national security. Confirmation of this in the conditions of globalization of world information processes is the fact that each state seeks to protect its own interests in the field of information policy. Ukraine, as a part of the world community, also seeks to protect its information space and potential from various types of information attacks.

Until 2014, Ukraine did not pay due attention to information security, which other countries took advantage of. But after the annexation of Crimea by the Russian Federation, Ukraine had to revise its information policy and National Security Strategy in general. As the scientist M. Dmytrenko rightly observes: «The nature and peculiarities of the conduct of the Russian-Ukrainian war show that its goal is to change the self-identification of the population and turn the Eastern region of our country into a «gray zone», which will leave the Russian Federation the levers of its influence due to the constant threat of spreading instability to all of Ukraine» [5, p. 236-243].

The full-scale invasion of the territory of Ukraine on February 24, 2022 by the Russian Federation was accompanied by aggressive and well-planned information propaganda in order to justify this step.

Among the reasons why Ukraine was not ready for such information attacks, the following can be distinguished:

- the Ukrainian information space turned out to be unprotected from external expansion;
- there is no Ukrainian national information product in the global media space, due to which the perception of our country in the rest of the world is formed through other resources that are not always true and objective;
- the activity of the domestic mass media regarding the systematic and objective coverage of facts and events lacks strategic planning.

If we talk about the methods of information attacks on the part of the Russian Federation, V. Husarov makes appropriate conclusions on this matter. The expert singles out the following directions of information and psychological attacks against Ukraine:

- formation of negative opinions about the military leadership of Ukraine, that the incompetent actions of the leadership lead to large losses among the military and the civilian population during the anti-terrorist operation;

- the spread of opinions about the demoralization of military units of the Ukrainian army in the East and about its inability to conduct combat operations;

- imposing the idea that Ukraine will not be able to do without Russian gas, and therefore it is necessary to return to revisions of gas contracts. In general, the so-called gas issue has been the object of manipulation and speculation throughout the period of Ukraine's independence (The Kremlin 2014).

To combat information attacks and to create a truly secure and favorable information environment, the first step is to create an effective regulatory framework. Today, the issue of information security is regulated in such normative legal acts as:

- in 1997, the National Security Concept of Ukraine was approved, however, the Information Security Concept of Ukraine was not created on the basis of this document, and the document itself has only a doctrinal character and serves as a basis for the further regulatory framework.

- in 2003, the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine adopts a fundamental legal act in the field of national security - the Law of Ukraine «On the Basics of National Security of Ukraine», however, information security is not given due attention. In 2009, the first state act in the field of information security appeared, which was signed by the President of Ukraine, and later the Doctrine of Information Security of Ukraine was adopted.

- In 2022, after the full-scale invasion of the Russian Federation, the President of Ukraine introduced the Decree «On the decision of the National Security and Defense Council of Ukraine» dated March 18, 2022 «Regarding the implementation of a unified information policy under martial law». It has been established that in the conditions of hostilities, the implementation of a unified information policy is a priority issue of national security, the provision of which is implemented by uniting all national TV channels in the project «Unified News #UARazom».

However, truly effective mechanisms for countering propaganda and information attacks appeared only in the National Security Strategy of Ukraine dated September 14, 2020. The Information Security Strategy, which was put into effect by the Decree of the President of Ukraine dated October 15, 2021 No. 685/2021, deserves special attention. One of the directions of the adopted Strategy is the use by the Russian Federation of hybrid war technologies against Ukraine, which turned the information sphere into a key arena of confrontation (On the decision of the National Security 2021). At the same time, Ukraine has significant risks in the information sphere (table 1).

Statistics of cyberattacks in relation to Ukraine

№ s/p	Sector	Number
1.	Government and government organizations	347
2.	Local authorities	276
3.	Security and defense sector	175
4.	Commercial organizations	127
5.	Energy sector	92
6.	Telecom	81
7.	Financial sector	30
8.	IT sector	25
9.	Mass media	15

Source: (State Service 2023).

Analyzing Table 1 and referring to the information of the State Service of Special Communications and Information Protection of Ukraine, it is proven that the number of cases of information attacks in 2023 compared to 2022 increased by 62.5% (State Service 2023). Experts explain this by an increase in the activity of cybercriminals during the period of active hostilities.

The most vulnerable areas for cyber attacks are government organizations, technology and media. Such actions of criminals create many negative consequences for the national and regional security of states (Platonenko 2015).

Understanding the danger and threat of information attacks on the state, one of the first orders adopted by the President of the United States of America D. Biden in 2021 was an order in the field of protecting the information environment and protecting the American people from cyber attacks: «Incremental improvements will not give us the security we need; instead, the Federal Government needs to make bold changes and make significant investments to protect the vital institutions that underpin the American way of life. The federal government must fully exercise its authority and resources to protect its computing systems, whether cloud, on-premise or hybrid. The scope of protection and security should include the systems that process data (information technology (IT)) and those that manage the vital mechanisms that ensure our secu-

urity (operational technology (OT)) (Information Security GSA Home 2021).

If we talk about the international experience in the field of information security, then two key models can be distinguished: the western democratic (the countries of Western Europe, the USA, Canada) and the totalitarian (China, Belarus, the Russian Federation and others). The difference lies in the approaches and methods of creating a favorable information field for the state. That is, the goal of the state is to create a safe information field, to protect against information attacks, but in compliance with all the principles of democracy, without restricting the freedom of speech of its citizens and mass media (Ostroukhai, Petryk, Prysiazhniuk 2010).

In countries with a totalitarian model, the principles of implementing fairly monocentric defensive and offensive doctrines dominate. Information is considered, first of all, as a weapon resource, as a means of influencing one's own citizens and actively protecting and countering external informational influences. The mass media are fully under the control of the state and are used as a propaganda mechanism for its own citizens. Observance of the principles of democracy and freedom of speech is not a priority task of the leadership of countries of the totalitarian model (Huang 2007)

A comparative analysis of the information provision of the USA, the People's Republic of China, and Ukraine is given in Table 2.

Table 2

Regulatory base and subjects of information provision USA, China and Ukraine

Criteria	USA	China	Ukraine
Normative base	US information security legislation consists of federal and state laws. This includes laws: «On improving information security» of 1997, «On computer fraud and abuse» of 1986, etc.	The main act in the field of information security of the People's Republic of China is the 2016 Law on Cyber Security. The Golden Shield Project, also known as the Great Firewall of China, a program for filtering Internet content in the PRC, is also being implemented in the PRC.	Information security of the state is regulated by the following laws: Law of Ukraine «On Information» of 1992 Law of Ukraine «On Information Protection in Information and Telecommunication Systems» of 1994 Law of Ukraine «On State Secrets» of 1994 Law of Ukraine «On Protection of Personal Data» of 2010 Decree of the President of Ukraine On the decision of the National Security and Defense Council of Ukraine dated March 18, 2022 «Regarding the implementation of a unified information policy under martial law».

<p>Main subjects in the field of information security</p>	<p>The main person in the field of information security, in particular, is the President of the United States, the Department of Homeland Security (DHS) and other federal agencies to conduct criminal investigations to neutralize cybercriminals, as well as technical experts who develop new tools to combat cybercrime.</p>	<p>The main guarantor of information security and control on the Internet is the Communist Party and the Central Military Council of the People's Liberation Army of China.</p> <p>In addition, relevant ministries are involved in this process, such as: the Bureau of Public Information and Network Security Supervision, the Ministry of State Security, the Ministry of Science and Technology of the People's Republic of China, as well as research institutes and centers specializing in information security, as well as the Information and the certification center, which are the only structure dealing with issues of ideological control of civil information technologies.</p>	<p>The Interdepartmental Commission on Information Policy and Information Security operates under the National Security and Defense Council (NSDC). Among its main tasks, in particular, is the analysis of the state and possible threats to Ukraine's national security in the information sphere and the generalization of international experience in the formation and implementation of information policy.</p> <p>The State Service for Special Communications and Information Protection of Ukraine is a subject of the defense and security sector and the main subject of the national cyber security system, coordinating the activities of cyber security entities in the field of cyber protection, communications administrator and regulator of communication services.</p> <p>Secretary of the National Security and Defense Council of Ukraine, who is responsible for the information policy of Ukraine under martial law.</p>
--	---	--	--

Source: [Dmytrenko], [Information], [Oliynyk], [On the State Service], [Dyusenov], [Prior]

The Interdepartmental Commission on Information Policy and Information Security operates under the National Security and Defense Council (NSDC). Among its main tasks, in particular, is the analysis of the state and possible threats to Ukraine's national security in the information sphere and the generalization of international experience in the formation and implementation of information policy.

The State Service for Special Communications and Information Protection of Ukraine is a subject of the defense and security sector and the main subject of the national cyber security system, coordinating the activities of cyber security entities in the field of cyber protection, communications administrator and regulator of communication services. Secretary of the National Security and Defense Council of Ukraine, who is responsible for the information policy of Ukraine under martial law.

Conclusions.

Thus, consideration of the information security features of Ukraine, the United States, and China made it possible to reach the following conclusions: 1) the national features of Ukraine, the United States, and China in the field of information security as a part of state sovereignty primarily consist in the difference in the regulatory and legal framework that facilitates or inhibits the implementation of the task of information security protection and state sovereignty;

2) a feature of the current state of Ukraine's information policy and, accordingly, its greater effectiveness, is a meaningful renewal of the joint action of the

country's government on the basis of relevant normative legal acts and relevant institutions related to the implementation of information policy;

3) the government should promote the activity of patriotic periodicals, audio and video content, support educated, literate media workers in order to raise the level of presentation of reliable information, which caused trust and respect for both information products of Ukraine and their producers;

4) civil society institutions should be involved in the common cause of protecting information and state sovereignty.

References

1. Dmytrenko, M. Problematic issues of information security of Ukraine. *International relations. Political science series*. 2017. No. 17. P. 236–243.
2. Dyusenov, N. Defending cyberspace: how China is pursuing a power strategy: 2023. *Sarbaz.kz editorial staff*. URL: <https://sarbaz.kz/mirovoj-vektor/519-zashchita-kiberprostranstva-kak-kitai-vystraivaet-sobstvennuiu-strategiiu/> (accessed 14 November 2023).
3. Huang, Qin. Information policy of the People's Republic of China in modern international relations: Diss. Ph.D. Sciences: 23.00.03 - 2007. URL: <http://www.disslib.org/informatsiy-na-polityka-kytajskoyi-narodnoyi-respubliki-v-suchasnykh-mizhnarodnykh.html> (accessed 26 November 2023).
4. Information security strategy of Ukraine, approved by the Decree of the President of Ukraine dated

15.10.2021 No. 685/2021. URL: <https://www.president.gov.ua/documents/6852021-41069> (accessed 12 December 2023).

5. Information Security GSA Home. 2021. URL: <https://www.gsa.gov/reference/gsa-privacy-program/information-security> (accessed 28 December 2023).

6. Law of Ukraine «On Information». Information of the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. 1992. URL: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2657-12> - Text (accessed 18 January 2024).

7. Oliynyk, O. Some actual problems of legal regulation of the information sphere in Ukraine. Scientific Bulletin of the Lviv State University of Internal Affairs. No. 2. 2011. P. 216.

8. On the decision of the National Security and Defense Council of Ukraine dated October 15, 2021: Decree of the President of Ukraine №685/2021. URL: <https://www.president.gov.ua/documents/6852021-41069> (accessed 5 February 2024).

9. On the national security of Ukraine: Law of Ukraine dated June 21, 2018 № 2469-VIII. URL: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2469-19> - Text (accessed 10 February 2024).

10. On the State Service of Special Communications and Information Protection of Ukraine: Law of Ukraine dated February 23, 2006. № 3475-IV. URL:

Slovak international scientific journal # 87, (2024). <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/3475-15> - Text (accessed 25 February 2024).

11. Ostroukhoi, V., Petryk, V., Prysiazhniuk, M. etc. ed., Information security (social and legal aspects): textbook. Kyiv. 2010.

12. Panchenko, O. Information security of a person: monograph. Kyiv 2011. P. 672.

13. Platonenko, A. Modern threats to information security for public and private institutions of Ukraine. Modern information protection. 2015. No. 4. P. 86-90.

14. Prior to the implementation of a unified information policy in the minds of the military camp. Decision of the RNBO dated 03/18/2022. URL: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/n0004525-22> - Text (accessed 21 April 2024).

15. State Service of Special Communications and Information Protection of Ukraine. Work report for 2023. URL: <https://scpc.gov.ua/api/files/9c21855d-74da-45d1-90f9-5d4f6795996a> (accessed 11 May 2024).

16. The Kremlin has launched a new information operation against Ukraine. (2014) *ms.detector.media* URL: <https://ms.detector.media/manipulyatsii/post/11351/2014-09-04-kreml-rozpochav-novu-informatsiyu-operatsiyu-proty-ukrainy-ekspert/> (accessed 24 May 2024).